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Abstract:

Herein, we report the synthesis of several magnetic carbon structures starting from spheres (CSs) to more elongated structures to get tubes and fibers by customizing chemical vapour deposition parameters. These CSs-based products, ranging from nano- to micro-size, were investigated by morphological point of view using scanning electron microscopy, energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy, and Raman spectroscopy. These carbon structures were combined with screen-printed electrodes highlighting their electrochemical effectiveness towards the detection of several species, i.e. ferricyanide, ascorbic acid, dopamine, cysteine, serotonin, and NADH. The presence of iron nuclei within the carbonaceous lattices, besides having improved the electrochemical performances at the printed electrodes, might confer these CSs-based structures a future application in the field of remediation/sensing. Herein, some preliminary applications were provided showing that these materials can be easily employed to collect species and, successively, coupled with printed electrochemical sensors.

Magnetic carbon spheres and their derivatives combined with printed electrochemical sensors

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Abstract

Herein, we report the synthesis of several magnetic carbon structures starting from spheres (CSs) to more elongated structures to get tubes and fibers by customizing chemical vapour deposition parameters. These CSs-based products, ranging from nano- to micro-size, were investigated by morphological point of view using scanning electron microscopy, energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy, and Raman spectroscopy. These carbon structures were combined with screen-printed electrodes highlighting their electrochemical effectiveness towards the detection of several species, i.e. ferricyanide, ascorbic acid, dopamine, cysteine, serotonin, and NADH. The presence of iron nuclei within the carbonaceous lattices, besides having improved the electrochemical performances at the printed electrodes, might confer these CSs-based structures a future application in the field of remediation/sensing. Herein, some preliminary applications were provided showing that these

1 materials can be easily employed to collect species and, successively, coupled with printed
2 electrochemical sensors.
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10 11 **1. Introduction** 12 13 14 15 16

17 After the discovery of fullerenes, the research activity has been focused on the possibility of
18 synthesizing other small size carbonaceous materials of variable shape. Among these, there are
19 spheres, tubes, fibers, and more recently graphene, all ranging in the ‘nano’ regime dimension [1-
20 3]. Beyond basic research, most of the success reached in practical applications relies on the good
21 control gained over the structural and morphological properties of the final carbon products.
22 Consequently, carbon-based nano-and micro-structures are now used as smart materials in several
23 applications such as catalysis, energy storage, renewable energy, remediation, sensing,
24 nanomedicine, and others [4-6]. Graphene and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are the most employed
25 materials thanks to their unique electric and mechanical properties, while applications of close-
26 curved nanostructures (e.g. fullerenes) are more limited [7, 8]. The carbon spheres (CSs) are closed
27 shell carbon-based material curved as fullerenes, but they differ from the fullerene’s family since
28 their inner structure is constituted of numerous graphitic sheets that can be found in ordered or
29 disordered arrangement forming, in this last case, unclosed shells that eventually create defective
30 reaction sites. Recently, there has been a renewed interest in CSs applications in electroanalytical
31 field since they display good chemical stability, low density, high surface-to-volume ratio, and
32 interesting electrochemical properties [9-13]. However, their better-known “brothers” i.e. graphene
33 and nanotubes (single and multi-walled) often hide the effectiveness of CSs. Herein, we highlight
34 the suitability of CSs-based materials to be exploited as electrochemical booster for screen-printed
35 electrodes (SPEs). To produce carbonaceous materials with different shaped structures, Chemical
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1 Vapour Deposition (CVD) was employed as the technique; in fact by selecting some experimental
2 parameters during CVD, i.e. gas flux, catalyst concentration, flow rate and duration, different
3 structures can be easily realized. In this work, four different types of configured CSs-based
4 structures were synthesized: spheres, aggregates, necklaces, and tubes. To evaluate their
5 electrochemical performances, SPEs were modified with stable dispersions of the synthesized CSs-
6 based structures and these miniaturized tools were tested in cyclic voltammetry using
7 ferro/ferricyanide as redox probe. In addition, the electroanalytical features of the various carbon
8 structures, ranging from zero dimensional (spheres) to three dimensional (networked tubes)
9 configurations, were also evaluated towards the detection of clinically relevant molecules, i.e.
10 ascorbic acid, dopamine, cysteine, serotonin, NADH, highlighting a clear enhancement if compared
11 with the bare SPEs.
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13 Besides the intrinsic electrochemical effectiveness of these structures, their magnetic nature makes
14 them suitable for application in the field of sensing and remediation. In principle, the magnetic
15 carbon-based structures might be adopted to capture target analytes (or pollutants) and successively
16 to detect those. This approach offers a step-forward for future applications, especially towards the
17 reduction of the operative extra-tasks at the end-user stage. In fact, one might imagine that the end-
18 user could use these materials to sample the analyte, even in a complex matrix, just by magnetically
19 collecting it, followed by the measurement of the “sampled” analyte by means of whichever device.
20 This approach was demonstrated through preliminary efforts: these magnetic CSs-based materials
21 were easily employed to sample species and, successively, coupled with electrochemical devices,
22 revealing the presence of the “sampled” species. As an outlook, the use of non-sophisticated
23 synthetic protocols allows for producing smart platforms that can be easily functionalized with
24 enzyme, antibody, and nucleic acids, for the development of CSs-based fully-enclosed bioassays.
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26 **2. Experimental section**

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2.1. Materials

All the reagents were of analytical grade and they were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (USA).

2.2. Screen-Printed Electrode Fabrication

SPEs was produced with a 245 DEK (Weymouth, UK) screen-printing machine. Graphite-based ink (Electrodag 423 SS) from Acheson (Milan, Italy) was used to print both the working and auxiliary electrode. Silver/silver chloride ink (Electrodag 477 SS) was used to print the pseudo-reference electrode. Flexible polyester film (Autostat HT5) purchased from Autotype Italia (Milan, Italy) was used as substrate. The diameter of the working electrode was 0.3 cm resulting in a geometric area of 0.07 cm².

2.3. Synthesis of CSs-based structures

All carbon-based structures were produced by using a floating catalyst. CVD was carried out in a quartz tube inserted in a furnace at 760 Torr pressure keeping the temperature at 800 °C. In particular, a solution of variable concentration (see Table 1), containing ferrocene dissolved in 1,2-dichlorobenzene was continuously injected (at a constant rate) with a glass syringe and carried into the hot reaction zone by a combined acetylene/argon gas flux. At the end of the synthesis process, the reaction products were collected from the quartz tube and used without post-growth purification. Table 1 reports the values of the growth parameters adopted for each sample produced.

2.4. Procedure for Preparation of CSs-Dispersions

10 mg of the selected powder were firstly dissolved in 5 mL of N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF), and subsequently 5 mL of distilled water were added. The mixture was then sonicated for 1 h at 59 kHz. The dispersion was stored in the dark at room temperature.

2.5. Procedure for SPE modification

1 SPEs were modified by drop casting. 6 μL of the dispersion were drop cast onto the working
2 electrode surface via three following steps of 2 μL . The modified SPEs were tested after the
3 evaporation of the solvent dispersion.
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10 **3. Results and discussion**

11 **3.1. CSs-based Structures Characterization**

12 In this work, we synthesized several CSs-based structures starting from 0D spheres to 3D networks
13 of tubes by CVD, as described in the experimental section. SEM analysis was performed to
14 investigate the morphology of the obtained carbon-based structures. Figure 1 reports a collection of
15 images sampled from the four different growth conditions, giving different products namely Sphere,
16 Aggregate, Necklace, and Tubes. As reported in Figure 1A, the sphere structure is perfectly shaped
17 and consists of individual particles, characterized by a mean diameter that ranges between 200 ± 10
18 nm (Figure 1A). The increase of both the ferrocene and the gas rate favoured the accretion of the
19 spheres with a mean diameter of 175 ± 10 nm (Figure 1B) as evaluated from a statistical analysis
20 obtained by the TEM studies [14]. The subsequent increase of the gas rate in the CVD chamber
21 allowed for generating a more complex structure, named Necklace where the spheres partially
22 welded forming long arrangements characterized by a high degree of surface roughness (Figure
23 1C). These Necklace structures have a mean diameter of 1.4 ± 0.2 μm with a length that can reach
24 20 μm , although they show a wide variety of outer diameter and most of them are full. Some tubes
25 exhibit the so-called Bamboo-shape and others are covered by carbon aggregates almost spherical
26 in shape that increase the outer surface roughness. A statistical analysis gives an average diameter
27 of 1.5 ± 0.3 μm , and a length longer than 30 μm (Figure 1D). In addition, some of these structures
28 showed a magnetic response and this behaviour can be ascribed to the presence of iron that is the
29 only magnetic element made available in the reaction process [14]. In this regard, the EDX analysis
30 confirmed the presence of iron (Supporting Information, Fig S1). The graphitic nature of these
31 carbon materials was investigated using the Raman spectroscopy (Figure 2). In particular, we
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1 focused on the D-band and G-band. The D-band arises from aromatic rings while the G-band
2 originates from the vibration of sp^2 -bonded carbon atom in a two-dimensional hexagonal lattice and
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4 represents the extent of graphitization. The structural quality was also analyzed from the I_D/I_G ratio.
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6 This parameter is widely used as a measure of the size of the sp^2 ring clusters in a network of sp^3 -
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8 and sp^2 -bonded carbons, giving information of structural distortions. The obtained values for the
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10 four samples range between 1.03-1.86. In particular, the lower value of 1.03 and 1.1 was found for
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12 the samples A and B, respectively. This ratio values are comparable to those reported in the
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14 literature for similar but no magnetic CSs [15, 16]. The intensity of the D and G bands is
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16 comparable for samples A and B, highlighting the presence of structural imperfections. The
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18 imperfections can be originated from the disorder in the graphene sheets relative orientation in the
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20 spheres as well as from the presence of pentagon and heptagon carbon rings that are necessary to
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22 bend the graphene during the spheres formation. Nonetheless, both the D and G peaks are sharp,
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24 suggesting the presence of mostly C sp^2 hybridization form in the nanostructure.
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31 The samples C and D have similar spectra that show a marked contribution from the D band
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33 with respect to the G band with a measured I_D/I_G ratio of 1.55 and 1.86, respectively.
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36 The G band of these two samples decreases in intensity and broadens. It can be noticed, that
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38 the D band for the four samples has always a marked intensity, due to the disorder and the
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40 change in the size distribution of the carbon nano-structures in the assembly.
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45 **3.2. Electrochemistry of the CSs-based Structures**

46 **3.2.1. Functionalization of the Printed Platforms**

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49 In order to characterize the CSs-based structures by an electrochemical point of view, the printed
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51 electrodes were modified by drop casting method with CSs dispersions (Figure 3). Briefly, all
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53 structures were dispersed in a solution made by 50% v/v water/ dimethylformamide, as previously
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55 reported for other carbon-based modifiers [17, 18], and SPEs were modified with these different
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1 dispersions (Sphere, Aggregate, Necklace, Tube) via three following steps of 2 μL , with the aim to
2 custom an easy and automatable way for miniaturized printed sensor manufacturing.
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7 **3.2.2. Heterogeneous Electron Transfer Constant Evaluation**

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9 To evaluate the electrochemical features of the different shaped materials, heterogeneous
10 electron transfer constant (k^0) was calculated using the inner-sphere ferro-/ferricyanide
11 redox couple [19, 20] and Nicholson method [21]. In detail, the following equation: $k^0 =$
12 $\Psi(D_O\pi\nu(nF/RT))^{0.5}(D_O/D_R)^{\alpha/2}$ was employed, where Ψ is the kinetic parameter that is
13 dependent on the separation between anodic and cathodic peaks, ΔE , D_R and D_O represent
14 the diffusion coefficients of the reduced and the oxidized specie, ν is the scan rate, F is the
15 Faraday constant, α is the transfer coefficient (0.5), and n is the number of electrons
16 transferred in the electrochemical process. In this regard, we obtained k^0 equal to
17 $(7.7\pm 1.3)10^{-3}$, $(6.0\pm 0.2)10^{-3}$, $(9.0\pm 1.0)10^{-3}$, $(5.0\pm 1.0)10^{-3}$ cm/s for sphere, aggregate,
18 necklace, and tube structures, respectively. Furthermore, due to the high peak-to-peak
19 separation of the unmodified SPE, it was not possible to calculate the k^0 for bare SPE,
20 highlighting the improvement of the electron transfer using SPEs modified with these
21 carbon structures.
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41 As an example, in Figure 4 we reported the electrochemical responses using SPEs modified
42 with sphere, aggregate, necklace, and tube structures in respect to the bare SPE at scan rate
43 of 0.05 V/s, to shed light the peak-to-peak separation and resolution of the peaks in the case
44 of modified SPEs. It is interesting to observe how these modifiers compare very favorably
45 with the others carbonaceous materials that have been utilized as electrode modifiers, i.e.
46 graphene oxide, reduced-graphene oxide, carbon nanotubes, as reported by our and others
47 research groups [22-25].
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3.3. Cyclic voltammetric study of modified-SPEs

With the aim of evaluating the CSs-based structures sensing properties, the different modified electrodes were tested towards relevant analytes in biomedical field namely ascorbic acid, dopamine, cysteine, serotonin, and NADH. In Figure 5 the cyclic voltammograms related to the above-cited species are displayed. From the results reported, it comes out that the change in the shape and complexity of the CSs-based structures shows a different electrochemical behaviour. In order to better understand the outcomes, in Table S1 (Supporting Information) all the overpotentials were reported. The voltammograms in Figure 5 clearly evidence the enhancement of electrochemical behaviour of the SPEs modified with magnetic CSs-based structures when compared with the voltammograms obtained using bare SPE. For all studied species, the overpotentials appear lower than those observed at the unmodified electrode (Table S1, Supporting Information), owing to the presence of modifiers. Although all structures displayed a decrease of the overpotential, they are characterized by slight differences which could be dependent on their specific shapes. This slight different electrochemical behaviour is ascribed to some key factors including the presence of iron nuclei, the defective sites of the carbon skeleton, and the outer surface roughness. For instance, the Necklace structures mainly exploit the highest overpotentials with respect to the other structures, considering all the species analyzed, e.g. cysteine needs of 0.68 V (vs Ag/AgCl) to be oxidized at Necklace-modified SPE, while when Sphere (Figure 1A), Aggregate (Figure 1B) or Tube (Figure 1D) are adopted as SPE modifier, the oxidation potential is 0.52, 0.54, and 0.51 V, respectively. This behaviour might be ascribed to the less defective surface that decreases the number of reactive sites. Instead, the other structures have similar overpotentials. However, the presence of iron nuclei would be considered the main responsible of the effects in improving electrochemistry of printed platforms. The iron nuclei impurities in the magnetic CSs-structures act as nanospot centers

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for redox reaction, as reported in other systems, i.e. dopamine at SWCNTs/iron (III) oxide, hydrogen peroxide at ferric hexacyanoferrate (Prussian Blue), oxygen at graphene-iron composite [26-28]. Again, the absence of iron nuclei (as in the case of the non-magnetic Aggregate structures) leads only to a negligible electrocatalysis improvement in respect to the bare SPE [14], allowing for a predominant effect of iron nuclei over the defect sites.

3.4. Exploitation of magnetic properties of CSs

It seems clear how the presence of the CSs-based modifiers allows for improving the electrochemical behaviour of the printed electrodes, both in terms of sensitivity and overpotential, with respect to the bare platform. Furthermore, the presence of iron nuclei in the above-cited structures confers to the CSs-based assemblies a clear magnetic feature. In Figure 6, a net example of the magnetic behaviour is reported. In this case, it is shown how the Aggregate structures can be easily attracted by an external magnet, exploiting their unique characteristics. In principle, these magnetic structures might be used separately from a SPE, for example for adsorbing species that are present in a sample; successively they can be re-concentrated on the SPE in order to carry out the detection, by exploiting their magnetic properties, as described in Figure 7.

Compared with existing technology based on the magnetic beads, which are widely used in the development of analytical assays i.e. immunologic, the magnetic CSs-based structures might be involved for the development of novel multi-task devices. In the previous section, their electroanalytical effectiveness has been proven. However, their relevance should not be focused solely over the possibility to improve the performance of SPE: to do this, a plethora of materials (not only carbon-based) can be taken into account. The real added value of these structures is that they are capable to accomplish three assignments, within the same object: 1) to sample a target molecule, 2) to be magnetically gathered on any substrate, and 3) to sense the “sampled”. This represents the most beneficial role that can be attributed to

1 these objects. In order to highlight this possibility, the magnetic Aggregate structures
2 displayed interesting adsorbing features. More precisely, ferricyanide, fuchsine, methylene
3 blue, and Prussian blue, were taken as model targets to be adsorbed and released. To carry
4 out these experiments 1 mg of magnetic Aggregate structures was immersed in a 3-mL
5 solution containing one of the above-cited species. After 10 minutes, the sample was
6 adsorbed on the Aggregate structures, dried, and magnetically concentrated on the white
7 spot. A 10- μ L drop of water was used to evaluate the release of the adsorbed molecules. As
8 illustrated in Figure 7A, the CSs-based structures were stirred for 10 minutes in a flask,
9 containing the sample to be collected. Successively, the Aggregate structures (with the
10 adsorbed molecules) were separated from the sample-containing flask with an external
11 magnet, dried, and deposited onto a white substrate, i.e. filter paper. As showed in Figure
12 7B, an external magnet was capable to move the magnetic CSs from a white spot to another.
13 Thanks to the magnetic guidance, the Aggregate structures remained fixed on a precise spot.
14 After a 10 μ L-drop of water has been added to the magnetic structures, the adsorbed species
15 were clearly released to the paper, evidenced with a change of color depending on the
16 released molecules (Figure 7C), demonstrating the relevant role in collecting and releasing
17 molecules. Successively, preliminary experiments were performed by collecting and
18 detecting ferricyanide electrochemically. To carry out this approach, the magnetic
19 Aggregates were immersed in the sample solution, freely to move. They were stirred in a
20 flask where the molecule to sample, i.e. ferricyanide, was present. Successively, the
21 Aggregate structures (with the adsorbed ferricyanide) were separated from the sample-
22 containing flask with an external magnet, dried, and deposited onto the three-configured
23 SPE, as displayed in Figure 8A. Lastly, the CSs-SPE was covered with a 50 μ L-drop of
24 phosphate buffer in order to allow the analyte to be detected. Figure 8B displays the
25 voltammograms obtained by exploiting the properties of the CSs structures, utilizing
26 different “sampling” periods, i.e. 10 and 30 minutes, and allowing an increasing of
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1 sensitivity at the increase of the sampling time. From these results, the analyte is sampled
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4 advantage of a completely integrated smart material.
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10 **4. Conclusions**

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12 In summary, this study provided an effective application in the electroanalytical field by
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14 interfacing magnetic carbon spheres with screen-printed electrodes as a model system.
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16 Different architectures have been characterized both morphologically and electrochemically.
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18 Through easy drop casting method, screen-printed electrodes have been efficiently modified
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20 with carbonaceous structures, which conferred to the electrodes a clear electrochemical
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22 enhancement, regarding the detection of relevant species such as ferro/ferricyanide, ascorbic
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24 acid, dopamine, cysteine, serotonin, and NADH. These magnetic microsized structures,
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26 thanks to their adsorbing properties and also to the presence of iron nuclei within the
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28 carbonaceous lattice, allowed for the development of a novel conceptual step forward in the
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30 field of sensing (and not only). The exploitation of their adsorptive, magnetic, and
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32 electrocatalytic features, offers the possibility to develop a novel analytical research line:
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34 these CSs-based magnetic structures can sample particular analytes and then being coupled
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36 with electrochemical external devices for detection. In this work, the suitability of these
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38 CSs-based products was positively demonstrated via preliminary efforts by combining them
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40 with printed electrodes. We are confident that these magnetic materials, assisted by the
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42 CVD synthetic approach, will be capable to provide the end-users an all-in-one platform,
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44 that has been demonstrated to be easily interfaced with sensing devices. Besides the
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46 promising results reached in this study, these smart materials might be coupled to
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48 biomolecules, i.e. enzymes, antibodies, in order to develop specific bioassays. For future
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1 studies, these smart materials will be functionalized with biomolecules to perform more
2 targeted biomedical and environmental assignments.
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15 **Supporting information**

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18 Supporting data regarding the EDX spectra of the magnetic structures and a table containing the
19 overpotentials required for the target analytes detection, are associated with this article can be found
20 in the online version.
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1 **Figure captions**
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3 **Figure 1.** SEM micrographs of A) Sphere, B) Aggregate, C) Necklace, and D) Tube
4 structures.
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9 **Figure 2.** Raman spectra of A) spheres, B) aggregates, C) necklaces, and D) tubes.
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12 **Figure 3.** A schematic representation of the production of a generic CSs-based dispersion in
13 a 1:1 DMF/water mixture, and the following SPE modification via drop casting approach.
14 Inset: a photographic image of the experimental setup and a major focus on the SPE and the
15 small potentiostat used to perform the experiments.
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22 **Figure 4.** Cyclic voltammograms recorded in presence of 1 mM of ferro/ferricyanide in 0.05
23 M phosphate buffer containing 0.1 M potassium chloride (pH 7.4). A) All the cyclic
24 voltammograms were recorded at scan rate of 50 mV/s using bare SPE (dashed line) or SPE
25 modified with magnetic CSs-based structures, i.e. Sphere (red line), Aggregate (green line),
26 Necklace (violet line), Tube (blue line).
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32 **Figure 5.** Cyclic voltammograms recorded in presence of 2 mM of A) ascorbic acid, B)
33 cysteine, C) dopamine, D) NADH, and E) serotonin. All the experiments were carried out in
34 0.05 M phosphate buffer containing 0.1 M potassium chloride (pH 7.4) at a scan rate of 50
35 mV/s using bare SPE (dashed line) or SPE modified with magnetic CSs-based structures, i.e.
36 Sphere (red line), Aggregate (green line), Necklace (violet line), Tube (blue line).
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43 **Figure 6.** Photograph of Aggregate structures before (A) and after (B) being attracted by an
44 outer magnet.
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49 **Figure 7.** A) A schematic representation of the experimental path followed to sample a
50 generic molecule on the Aggregate magnetic structures, and successively released on the
51 paper-based substrate, i.e. filter paper. B) Photographs regarding the capacity of the
52 Aggregate structures to be magnetically driven and concentrated onto a substrate. C) Release
53 of the adsorbed ferricyanide (10 mM), fuchsine (0.1 mg/mL), methylene blue (0.1 mg/mL),
54 and Prussian blue (0.1 mg/mL). To carry out these experiments 1 mg of magnetic Aggregate
55 structures have been immersed in a 3-mL solution containing one of the above-cited species.
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1 After 10 minutes, the sample has been adsorbed on the Aggregate structures, dried, and
2 magnetically concentrated on the white spot. A 10- μ L drop of water was used to evaluate
3 the release of the adsorbed molecules.
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7 **Figure 8.** A) A schematic representation of the experimental path followed to collect a
8 ferricyanide on the Aggregate CSs and release the same molecule on a printed electrode, i.e.
9 SPE. B) Electrochemical detection by using a bare SPE without Aggregate CSs (black line)
10 and in presence of 1 mg of Aggregate CSs that have been immersed for 10 (red line) and 30
11 (green line) minutes in a 3-mL solution containing 10 mM ferricyanide. The SPEs were
12 covered with a 50- μ L drop of phosphate buffer prior the measurement was started. Cyclic
13 voltammograms have been carried out at a scan rate of 50 mV/s.
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21 **Table 1.** Detailed list of the sample preparation components used in the synthesis of the carbon
22 nanostructures.
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Table 1

Sample	Ar/C ₂ H ₂ [sccm]	Concentration of solution [M]	Rate [mL/h]
Sphere	50/25	0.21	3
Aggregate	250/40	0.27	4
Necklace	300/100	0.27	4.5
Tube	500/100	0.19	6.2

Figures

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Supplementary Materials

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